

Studies on synthesis of novel low molecular weight anthraquinone disperse dyes and their application on polyester and nylon

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Abstract : A series of novel disperse dyes has been prepared by subsequent reaction of 2-(2'-anthraquinonylamino-3'-hydroxy)-4-anilino-6-chloro-s-triazine with various amines. All the disperse dyes were characterized by their percentage yield, melting point, nitrogen elemental analysis, infrared spectrum, ¹H NMR data and dyeing performance on polyester and nylon fabrics. The percentage dye bath exhaustion on both the fabrics was found to be reasonably good and the dyed fabrics showed fair to good fastness to light and very good to excellent fastness to washing and rubbing.

Keywords : 2-Amino-3-hydroxyanthraquinone, nylon, polyester, dyeing properties.

Introduction

Anthraquinone dyes are the major chemical class of disperse dyes. The brilliant red, blue and turquoise anthraquinone dyes have great industrial significance. Heterocycles have been put to much use in the chemistry of disperse dyes¹. Disperse dyes have a limited solubility in water and they are essentially low molecular weight derivatives of azo, anthraquinone and other compounds, some particular disperse dye molecules may still be occluded onto fiber surface after the dyeing is completed^{2,3}. The continuously increasing demands and developments in the synthetic fibres, together with modification in the application and finishing techniques have necessitated a constant search for newer disperse dyes with novel structures to satisfy the requisite standards as regards the dyeing and fastness properties. With the rapid development of polyester microfibres, there is an urgent need to develop suitable disperse dyes⁴.

A large number of anthraquinonoid disperse dyes containing triazinyl moieties have been reported for obtaining yellow, orange, red, violet and blue shades on synthetic fibres. A majority of them have been derived from 1-amino-4-hydroxyanthraquinone^{5,6}, 1,4-diaminoanthraquinone^{7,8}, 1-aminoanthraquinones^{9,10}, 4,8-diamino-1,5-dihydroxyanthraquinone and their substituent derivatives. Monoazo disperse dyes represent the largest single group in which a relatively simple synthesis enable a range

of shades from greenish yellow to cyan to be produced with this chromophoric system^{11,12}.

John Blackwell¹³ synthesized blue anthraquinone disperse dyes which are used to dye or print cotton, polyester or polyester-cotton blends in fast deep blue shades. Anthraquinone dyes provide a number of bright fast to light blue and green neither available among the azo dyes nor in fact equalled by any other class. The colour of anthraquinone dyes depends upon substitution among definite lines^{14,15}. Anthraquinone nucleus has been of immense importance due to their light fastness properties and commercial value. The introduction of various groups in cyanuric chloride nucleus imparts fibre solubility to the molecules and helps fibre to pick up dye molecule and retain it, for very good wash fastness and light fastness properties. Looking to the above said advantages, in this paper we report the synthesis and study of the dyeing properties of low molecular weight anthraquinone disperse dyes based on 2-(2'-anthraquinonylamino-3'-hydroxy)-4-anilino-6-chloro-s-triazine systems.

Material and method :

Melting points (m.p.) were determined by open capillary method. Nitrobenzene, acetone and other chemicals used were of analytical grade. Cyanuric chloride was purified by recrystallization from pure benzene. The purity of all the dyes has been checked by TLC¹⁶. IR spectra were recorded in KBr on a Perkin-Elmer Model-881

spectrophotometer¹⁷ and PMR spectra on a Bruker DXR-300 (300 MHz FTNMR) instrument using TMS as internal standard and DMSO as solvent¹⁸. Absorption spectra were recorded in DMF on a Beckman DB-GT Grating spectrophotometer. The light fastness was assessed in accordance with BS : 1006-1978¹⁹. The rubbing fastness test was carried out with a Crockmeter (Atlas) in accordance with AATCC-1961 and the wash fastness test in accordance with IS : 765-1976.

Preparation of 2-(2'-anthraquinonylamino-3'-hydroxy)-4,6-dichloro-s-triazine (A) :

Cyanuric chloride (1.84 g, 0.01 mol) was stirred in acetone (25 ml) at a temperature below 5 °C for a period of an hour. A neutral solution of 2-amino-3-hydroxyanthraquinone (2.3 g, 0.01 mol) in aqueous sodium carbonate solution (10% w/v) was then added in small lots in about an hour. The pH was maintained at 5.5 to 6.5 during addition. The stirring was continued for four hours below 5 °C. The mixture was filtered and washed with petroleum ether, dried and used for subsequent condensation reaction. IR (cm⁻¹) : 1670 (>C=O), 1489 (-NH), 3455 and 3488 (-OH and -NH), 872 (C-Cl); ¹H NMR δ (ppm) : 3.45 (1H, s, -OH), 3.90 (1H, s, -NH), 6.80-7.89 (6H, m, Ar-H).

Preparation of 2-(2'-anthraquinonylamino-3'-hydroxy)-4-anilino-6-chloro-s-triazine (B) :

2-(2'-Anthraquinonylamino-3'-hydroxy)-4,6-dichloro-

s-triazine (3.87 g, 0.01 mol) was suspended in acetone (40 ml). To this suspension, aniline (1.39 g, 0.01 mol) was added in small lots. The mixture was heated upto 45-50 °C for three hours, cooled to room temperature, filtered, dried and used for subsequent reaction. IR (cm⁻¹) : 1668 (>C=O), 1483 (-NH), 3450 and 3483 (-OH and -NH), 868 (C-Cl); ¹H NMR δ (ppm) : 3.50 (1H, s, -OH), 3.89 (2H, s, -NH), 6.88-7.75 (11H, m, Ar-H).

Reaction of 2-(2'-anthraquinonylamino-3'-hydroxy)-4-anilino-6-chloro-s-triazine with various amines :

Preparation of D₁ :

2-(2'-Anthraquinonylamino-3'-hydroxy)-4-anilino-6-chloro-s-triazine (4.44 g, 0.01 mol) was suspended in nitrobenzene (60 ml). To this suspension *p*-nitroaniline (1.42 g, 0.01 mol) was added and the temperature was raised to 60-65 °C. The mixture was stirred at this temperature for five hours. The yellow product obtained was filtered, washed and crystallized from toluene. D₁ : IR (cm⁻¹) : 1671 (>C=O), 1493 (-NH), 1320 (N=O), 3450 and 3490 (-OH and -NH); ¹H NMR δ (ppm) (DMSO-*d*₆) : 3.42 (1H, s, -OH), 3.89 (3H, s, -NH), 6.85-7.99 (15H, m, Ar-H).

Following above procedure other disperse dyes D₂ to D₁₅ were synthesized using various primary amines shown in Table 1.

Table 1. Characterization data for disperse dyes D₁ to D₁₅

Dye no.	Coupling components (R)	Yield (%)	Mol. weight	m.p. (°C)	R _f value	Elemental Analysis of N (%)	
						Found	Required
D ₁	<i>p</i> -Nitroaniline	84	545	252	0.69	17.96	17.98
D ₂	3,5-Dinitro-2-aminophenol	77	606	229	0.82	18.45	18.48
D ₃	2,4-Dinitroaniline	83	590	259	0.47	18.93	18.98
D ₄	2-Chloro-4-nitroaniline	84	580	215	0.61	16.88	16.91
D ₅	<i>m</i> -Aminophenol	80	516	230	0.52	16.26	16.28
D ₆	4-Chloro-2,5-dimethoxyaniline	79	595	245	0.43	14.10	14.12
D ₇	6-Bromo-2,4-dinitroaniline	76	669	209	0.82	16.68	16.74
D ₈	2-Amino-5-nitrophenol	80	561	227	0.68	17.42	17.48
D ₉	2-Chloro-6-bromo- <i>p</i> -nitroaniline	85	659	240	0.67	14.81	14.88
D ₁₀	<i>p</i> -Chloroaniline	81	535	227	0.53	17.70	17.72
D ₁₁	2-Amino-4,6-dichlorophenol	83	585	250	0.59	14.35	14.38
D ₁₂	2,6-Dibromo- <i>p</i> -nitroaniline	80	689	205	0.44	12.14	12.19
D ₁₃	2,6-Dichloro- <i>p</i> -nitroaniline	76	616	263	0.53	15.91	15.93
D ₁₄	4-Nitro-2-aminophenol	78	563	235	0.63	17.37	17.41
D ₁₅	2-Amino-4-methyl-6-nitrophenol*	75	575	210	0.71	17.02	17.04

where R = various amines as coupling components for the formation of D₁ to D₁₅ (Table 1).

Results and discussion

A series of disperse dyes was prepared in order to evaluate their stability for dyeing polyester and nylon fabrics. The structure of the dyes were postulated and then established based on the analytical and spectral evidences.

Spectral data of D₂ to D₁₅ :

D₂ : ν_{\max} (KBr) (cm⁻¹) : 1675 (>C=O), 1449 (-NH), 1330 (-N=O), 3444 and 3495 (-OH and -NH); δ_{H} (DMSO-*d*₆) : 3.29 (1H, s, -OH), 3.85 (3H, s, -NH), 6.88–8.11 (13H, m, Ar-H).

D₃ : ν_{\max} (KBr) (cm⁻¹) : 1695 (>C=O), 1433 (-NH), 1339 (-N=O), 3450 and 3489 (-OH and -NH); δ_{H} (DMSO-*d*₆) : 3.42 (1H, s, -OH), 3.92 (3H, s, -NH), 6.85–8.09 (14H, m, Ar-H).

D₄ : ν_{\max} (KBr) (cm⁻¹) : 1705 (>C=O), 1463 (-NH), 1307 (-N=O), 3445 and 3497 (-OH and -NH), 765 (C-Cl); δ_{H} (DMSO-*d*₆) : 3.49 (1H, s, -OH), 3.89 (3H, s, -NH), 6.89–8.15 (14H, m, Ar-H).

D₅ : ν_{\max} (KBr) (cm⁻¹) : 1676 (>C=O), 1495 (-NH), 3450 and 3490 (-OH and -NH); δ_{H} (DMSO-*d*₆) : 3.25 (2H, s, -OH), 4.11 (3H, s, -NH), 6.79–8.18 (15H, m, Ar-H).

D₆ : ν_{\max} (KBr) (cm⁻¹) : 1685 (>C=O), 1493 (-NH), 3023 and 3010 (C-H) 3455 and 3497 (-OH and -NH), 765 (C-Cl); δ_{H} (DMSO-*d*₆) : 3.44 (1H, s, -OH), 3.96 (3H, s, -NH), 2.49 (6H, s, -OCH₃), 6.91–8.14 (13H, m, Ar-H).

D₇ : ν_{\max} (KBr) (cm⁻¹) : 1695 (>C=O), 1476 (-NH), 1300 (-N=O), 3449 and 3493 (-OH and -NH); δ_{H} (DMSO-*d*₆) : 3.48 (1H, s, -OH), 3.98 (3H, s, -NH), 6.85–7.99 (13H, m, Ar-H).

D₈ : ν_{\max} (KBr) (cm⁻¹) : 1697 (>C=O), 1490 (-NH), 1330 (-N=O), 3452 and 3490 (-OH and -NH); δ_{H} (DMSO-*d*₆) : 3.49 (2H, s, -OH), 4.01 (3H, s, -NH), 6.87–8.13 (14H, m, Ar-H).

D₉ : ν_{\max} (KBr) (cm⁻¹) : 1705 (>C=O), 1465 (-NH), 1338 (-NO), 3440 and 3489 (-OH and -NH), 755 (C-Cl); δ_{H} (DMSO-*d*₆) : 3.39 (1H, s, -OH), 4.13 (3H, s, -NH), 6.79–7.96 (13H, m, Ar-H).

D₁₀ : ν_{\max} (KBr) (cm⁻¹) : 1697 (>C=O), 1493 (-NH), 3450 and 3490 (-OH and -NH), 765 (C-Cl); δ_{H} (DMSO-*d*₆) : 3.40 (1H, s, -OH), 3.90 (3H, s, -NH), 6.85–7.97 (15H, m, Ar-H).

D₁₁ : ν_{\max} (KBr) (cm⁻¹) : 1667 (>C=O), 1494 (-NH), 3350 and 3480 (-OH and -NH), 755 (C-Cl); δ_{H} (DMSO-*d*₆) : 3.42 (2H, s, -OH), 4.07 (3H, s, -NH), 6.85–8.09 (13H, m, Ar-H).

D₁₂ : ν_{\max} (KBr) (cm⁻¹) : 1685 (>C=O), 1493 (-NH), 1313 (-N=O), 3350 and 3450 (-OH and -NH); δ_{H} (DMSO-*d*₆) : 3.44 (1H, s, -OH), 3.94 (3H, s, -NH), 6.91–8.14 (13H, m, Ar-H).

D₁₃ : ν_{\max} (KBr) (cm⁻¹) : 1695 (>C=O), 1487 (-NH), 1339 (-N=O), 3455 and 3497 (-OH and -NH), 767 (C-Cl); δ_{H} (DMSO-*d*₆) : 3.39 (1H, s, -OH), 3.90 (3H, s, -NH), 6.85–8.17 (13H, m, Ar-H).

D₁₄ : ν_{\max} (KBr) (cm⁻¹) : 1667 (>C=O), 1496 (-NH), 1339 (-N=O), 3400 and 3500 (-OH and -NH), 750 (C-Cl); δ_{H} (DMSO-*d*₆) : 3.30 (2H, s, -OH), 4.07 (3H, s, -NH), 6.86–8.13 (14H, m, Ar-H).

D₁₅ : ν_{\max} (KBr) (cm⁻¹) : 1685 (>C=O), 1493 (-NH), 1320 (-N=O), 3350 and 3450 (-OH and -NH), 2815, 2993 (C-H); δ_{H} (DMSO-*d*₆) : 3.40 (2H, s, -OH), 4.11 (3H, s, -NH), 1.01 (3H, s, -CH₃), 6.89–8.11 (13H, m, Ar-H).

Dyeing procedure :

All the dyes were applied on polyester and nylon by using standard procedure as given here. The fabric was dyed with 2.0% dye (calculated on weight of the fabric), 1% Dadamol dispersing agent, kept at a liquor ratio of 1 : 50. The process was started at 60 °C, the temperature was then raised at a rate of 2 °C per minute up to a final temperature of 120 °C and maintained at 120 °C by the automatic device. The process was continued for 60 min at 120 °C under pressure, after cooling the fabric was taken out and treated with a solution of detergent, the fabric was rinsed and dried at 60 °C²⁰ (Table 2).

The level dyeing, excellent disperse ability and dye ability proves that the dyes have optimum molecular weight. The yield of the dyes ranges 75 to 85%. The difference in the colour of newly synthesized dyes depends upon the substituents present and the position of the substituents on the rings. D₁ to D₁₅ gives light yellow to orange shades (Table 3). The shades are deeper in the case of polyester than on nylon which may be attributed to the possibility of large number of H-bonding.

Table 2. Materials and conditions for 2% shade on polyester and nylon

Materials	Polyester	Nylon
Weight of the fabric (g)	2.0	2.0
Amount of the dye under study (mg)	40	40
Glauber's salt solution (20% w/v) (ml)	-	1.5
Formic acid solution (10% w/v) (ml)	-	1.5
Dispersing agent Dadamol (mg)	100	-
MLR	1 : 50	1 : 40
Total volume of the solution in dye bath (ml)	100	80
pH of the dye bath	4.0	3.0
Dyeing temperature (°C)	120	100
Time of dyeing (min)	80	60

Table 3. Shade, percentage exhaustion and fixation of disperse dyes on polyester and nylon

Dye no.	Shade on dyed fibre	Exhaustion (%)		Fixation (%)	
		Polyester	Nylon	Polyester	Nylon
D ₁	Lemon yellow	79.10	69.95	92.92	82.20
D ₂	Light yellow	75.80	69.85	89.05	80.88
D ₃	Brownish yellow	76.30	76.45	91.09	87.64
D ₄	Greenish yellow	74.60	74.93	90.42	85.41
D ₅	Dark greenish yellow	79.78	74.60	93.38	89.14
D ₆	Brownish yellow	80.30	73.15	92.78	84.76
D ₇	Brownish yellow	77.18	70.80	87.46	81.21
D ₈	Light brownish yellow	72.63	74.28	95.00	86.17
D ₉	Light brownish yellow	81.30	75.33	91.02	90.90
D ₁₀	Brownish yellow	75.35	71.05	88.25	83.04
D ₁₁	Dark brownish yellow	70.80	72.65	86.86	88.09
D ₁₂	Fluorecent yellow	67.87	75.30	90.60	86.32
D ₁₃	Light orange	71.78	71.75	89.16	82.92
D ₁₄	Yellow	73.90	68.20	89.30	79.91
D ₁₅	Dark orange	70.13	77.15	89.13	87.44

Exhaustion study of dye bath :

Exhaustion is the percentage of dye absorbed on the fibre at the end of dyeing process. After diluting the liquor and washing to 250 ml, 5 ml of this solution was then diluted to 25 ml with water. The percentage dye bath exhaustion was calculated by measuring the absorbance of the above solution and reading the corresponding concentration on the calibration curve (Concentration → Absorbance). The results of the exhaustion study of each dye are presented in Table 3.

The results of the exhaustion and fixation study reveal that exhaustion and fixation on polyester is comparatively

better than nylon (Table 3). The percentage exhaustion of 2% dyeing on polyester fabric 2-chloro-6-bromo-*p*-nitroaniline based dye (D₉) shows maximum exhaustion 81.30% and 2,6-dibromo-*p*-nitroaniline based dye (D₁₂) shows minimum exhaustion 67.87%, while for nylon fabric 2,4-dinitroaniline based dye (D₃) shows maximum exhaustion 76.45% and 4-nitro-2-aminophenol based dye (D₁₄) shows minimum exhaustion 68.20%.

Fixation of dye :

Fixation is the percentage of dye chemically bonded to the fibre at the end of dyeing process. After dyeing the fabric was rinsed in water. Dyed pattern (0.1 g) was placed in a corning tube and sulphuric acid (10 ml) was poured over it. The fabric was stirred in sulphuric acid at room temperature for about 10–15 min. The solution was diluted to 50 ml with sulphuric acid. The percentage fixation of the dye was then calculated by measuring the absorbance of this solution and reading the corresponding concentration on the calibration curve (Concentration → Absorbance). A solution of the same amount of undyed fabric in sulphuric acid (50 ml) was used as reference solution in colourimetric estimation. The results of the fixation study of each dye are presented in Table 3.

The percentage fixation of 2% dyeing on polyester fabric 2-amino-5-nitrophenol based dye (D₈) shows maximum fixation 95.00% while the 2-amino-4,6-dichlorophenol based dye (D₁₁) shows minimum fixation 86.86%, for nylon fabric 2-chloro-6-bromo-*p*-nitroaniline based dye (D₉) shows maximum fixation 90.90% and 4-nitro-2-aminophenol based dye (D₁₄) shows minimum fixation 79.91. These practical data indicate that the synthesized dyes can be of commercial value in the related industries.

Study of light fastness :

The light fastness properties of dyed-patterns are commonly studied by automatic devices known as fadeometers. Xeno-test machine is a much better instrument for this purpose. For the present study the improved tests were carried out using daylight as a source of light. This requires use of standard dyed-pattern with increasing light fastness properties. Such standard samples are available and are made by the procedures according to the specifications laid down by the international organization for the standardisation (I.S.O.). These standard samples have

Reaction Scheme

light fastness properties rated from 8 to 1, the order indicating a decrease in the fastness properties.

All the dyes show generally moderate to very good light fastness properties (Table 4). The light fastness rating of all the dyes were found to be in the range of 3-6 for polyester and nylon which shows generally moderate

to very good light fastness properties.

Study of wash fastness :

Fastness to washing is dependent on the substantivity and polarity of the dye molecule and also on the fibre morphology. A soap solution, which was recommended for I.S.O. test was prepared by dissolving soap (5 g) in

Table 4. Fastness properties of disperse dyes on polyester and nylon

Dye no.	Light fastness		Wash fastness		Rubbing fastness			
	Polyester	Nylon	Polyester	Nylon	Dry		Wet	
					Polyester	Nylon	Polyester	Nylon
D ₁	4-5	5	3-4	4	4	4-5	3	4
D ₂	5	4-5	4	5	3	4	3-4	3-4
D ₃	5-6	3-4	5	4-5	4-5	3	4-5	4-5
D ₄	5	4	4	4	3-4	3-4	4	5
D ₅	3-4	4	4	3	4	4-5	4-5	5
D ₆	4	5-6	5	4	5	5	3-4	4-5
D ₇	5-6	5-6	5	4	5	5	4	3-4
D ₈	5	6	4-5	4-5	4-5	4	3	3
D ₉	4	4-5	3-4	5	3-4	4	3-4	4
D ₁₀	3-4	4	5	4	3-4	3-4	4	4-5
D ₁₁	5	3-4	5	4	4	4-5	4-5	3-4
D ₁₂	5-6	3-4	5	3	5	5	5	4-5
D ₁₃	5	4	4	3	4	4	4	5
D ₁₄	4	4	3-4	4	4	4	5	4
D ₁₅	4	3-4	4	4-5	5	4-5	5	4

Light fastness : 1 - poor, 2 - slight, 3 - moderate, 4 - fair, 5 - good, 6 - very good, 7 - excellent fastness and 8 - maximum fastness.

Wash and rubbing fastness : 1 - poor, 2 - fair, 3 - good, 4 - very good, 5 - excellent.

distilled water (100 ml). The test dyed pattern was then treated with 20 ml of the soap solution for 45 min at 50 °C after treatment; the test pattern was removed from soap solution bath and washed for 5-10 min in cold running tap water. The pattern was squeezed and dried at 50 °C. Loss in depth in shade of the pattern was assessed with grey scale (alternation of grade 1 to 5).

The washing fastness properties range from good to excellent fastness on polyester and nylon shown in Table 4. The wash fastness rating of all the dyes were found to be in the range of 3-5 for polyester and nylon which shows good to excellent wash fastness properties.

Study of dry and wet rubbing (crocking) fastness :

The specimens were fastened in the crockmeter apparatus which causes a piece of standard of white cloth (starch free 96 × 100 cotton fabrics long type) to rub against the coloured specimen under controlled condition of pressure and speed. The rubbing finers are covered with white cloth, both for the dry test and wet test, and slight back and forth for 20 rubbing strokes. The colour transferred to the white cloth was compared with grey scale.

The rubbing (dry and wet) fastness rating of all the

dyes were found to be in the range of 3-5 polyester and nylon (Table 4) which shows good to excellent rubbing fastness properties.

Conclusion :

The principle advantages of anthraquinone dyes are brightness and good fastness properties, including light and wash fastness. The shades of 2-(2'-anthraquinonylamino-3'-hydroxy)-4-anilino-6-chloro-s-triazine based anthraquinone disperse dyes varied from yellow to orange depending upon the position of the substituents present and/or the position of the primary amines. Dyes were prepared by conventional methods and their properties were examined both in solution and on application to nylon and polyester fabric. Within the range of dyes investigated, a gamut of colour variation on polyester fabric with excellent affinity and intensity of colour were observed. Furthermore these dyes show level dyeing, excellent disperse ability and dye ability. Exhaustion and fixation of these dyes are very good, this indicates that the dyes have good compatibility with the fabric. The remarkable degree of levelness after washing indicates good penetration and affinity of these dyes to the fabric. The optimum molecular weight provided level dyeing and excellent light and wash fastness properties. These prac-

tical data indicate that the synthesized dyes can be of commercial value in the related industries.

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